

FOREST4EU partner: GIS
 OG: DIGIGOZD
 OG's country: Slovenia
 Type of Innovation: Service

SiWaWa

Introduction

As part of the MOTI mobile application, a SiWaWa simulator has been created, which shows us the development of forests in the next 30 years. SiWaWa is intended for the simulation of development in one-dimensional and pure stands, where the parameters are like average stands. With the help of the SiWaWa application, we determine the type, amount, and time of implementation of silvicultural measures for a certain stand. We can decide based on the set wood production goals, which measure makes the most sense and what we will achieve with it.

Lessons learned

For the owner, data such as wood production goals or measures are important when planning the yield of the forest. The newer version of the SiWaWa growth simulator is available as a stand-alone mobile application, allowing the owner to obtain simulation results while in the field, directly after recording a stand with the MOTI application.

For further information contact

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The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<http://digigozd.si/>

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